

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

III TRENDS AND CULTURE MANAGEMENT COLLOQUIUM

RE:TREND

CULTURE IN MOTION

UNIVERSIDADE
DE LISBOA

LETRAS
LISBOA

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

III TRENDS AND CULTURE MANAGEMENT COLLOQUIUM

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Schedule	Session Name	Presentations (titles and authors)
session #1 11:30 – 12:45	Global Flows: Moving Cultures, Shifting Ecologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When Culture Moves: Cultural Motion and the Global Commodification of Indian Practices — Archisha Mazumdar, Krishnapriya TK • Indigenous Wellness Trends: Mediated Representations of Ayurveda in India — Subin Paul • The Cry of the Whales: Sociosemiotic Analysis of More-than-Human Agency in Platformized Climate Activism — Beatriz de Urquijo Isoard
session #2 14:00 – 15:15	The Algorithmic Turn: AI, Media and Creative Futures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reading the Algorithmic Zeitgeist: Trend Studies as a Compass for the AI–Journalism Nexus — Ana Marta M. Flores • Powerful Storytelling in the AI Era — Gemma Vallet • AI-Generated Cinema and the Future of Cultural Criticism — Sofia Alvarez Salas • Trends on Websummit 2025 — Illa Branco
session #3 15:15 – 16:30	Tradition Reloaded: Craft, Heritage & Future Imaginaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tradition and emergent technologies: AI's Role in Contemporary Arts & Crafts — André Matos • Between Tradition and Transformation: Media in Bhutan and the Negotiation of Global Trends — Szymon Zylinski • Futourism em Portugal: Vanguarda, Culpa ou Negócio de Branding Cultural? — Manuel Pinto Grunfeld
session #4 16:45 – 18:00	Embodied Styles: Fashion, Identity & Semiotic Codes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vestuário esportivo como mídia: atletas-ícones na construção estética do tênis feminino — Thaissa Schneider • Práticas culturais e indivíduos modernos: relações entre consumo e identidade LGBTQI+ — Nicolas Santos Nunes • James Bond – 007 a Marca que nunca passa de Moda — Filipa Moreira • Tendências e Humanidades Digitais: Novos Caminhos da Moda com Inteligência Artificial e Simulação 3D — Macivaldo Santana dos Santos
session #5A* 18:00 – 19:15	Strategic Trends: Organizations, Innovation & Performance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges and Strategies for Implementing Trend Methodologies in Organizations — Juliano Lira Guzzo, Romário Vieira Souza • Integrating Strategic Foresight into Technology Roadmapping — Wilson Silva Prata, Juliano Lira Guzzo • The fall of Trend Reports as a strategic instrument of cultural analysis and communication — Nelson Pinheiro Gomes • Tech Keynotes as Performative Spaces: Mapping the Spectacle-Driven Diffusion of Innovations — Suzana Cohen

<p>session #5B* 18:00 – 19:15</p>	<p>Decolonial Sensibilities: Fandoms, Feelings & Futures</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tensões entre a perspectiva decolonial indígena e o conceito de “novo” na moda e nos estudos de tendências — Miruna Raimundi de Gois, Daniela Novelli • Singing the Sensitive in the Age of Algorithms: Building Laufey’s Fandom Through Streaming Platforms — Fátima Meléndez Gómez • Forever Twilight in Forks: Vinte Anos de Fandom e Cultura Participativa — Susana Samagaia Garcia da Silva
<p>session #5C* 18:00 – 19:15</p>	<p>Politics of Style: Futures, Masculinities & Belonging</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Macrotendências e Política: Compreender a Representação LGBTQIA+ no Policymaking — João Miguel Abreu Miranda • From Metrosexual to Mainstream: The Evolution of Male Grooming Advertising in Indian Media — Twinkle Soni • From climate misinformation to futures literacy: rethinking communication in the age of cultural uncertainty — Tamara Natale de Moraes • O Interior como propulsor de Futuros Possíveis — Aline Moreira Monçores, Claudia Alquezar Facca
<p>session #6 19:15 – 20:30</p>	<p>Platformed Rhetorics: Stories, Signals & Semiotics</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Narrative-Based, Multidirectional Trends — Claire Haas • Mirrored rhetoric and cyclical monologues: Social media, trends, and algorithmic structuring of online messages — Julianna Kirschner • Cultural tension as a semiotic unit: contributions to a cultural epistemology of trends — William Cantú • Contribuições semióticas para o estudo das relações entre consumo e tendências — Matheus da Silva Duarte

O Interior como propulsor de Futuros Possíveis

Aline Moreira Monçores, Claudia Alquezar Facca

O interior, frequentemente associado à preservação de tradições e modos de vida locais, também se revela como território fértil para a inovação e a construção de futuros. Mais do que espaço periférico em relação aos grandes centros urbanos, o interior de Portugal apresenta-se como ecossistema vivo em constante transformação, articulando saberes ancestrais, práticas culturais e processos produtivos. Este estudo reflete sobre o papel do interior como célula de manutenção da tradição que se alinha à inovação para construir futuros possíveis.

Nesse sentido, a Beira Interior emerge como espaço estratégico para repensar modelos de produção e consumo em consonância com desafios globais, como a transição energética, a economia circular e a valorização da cultura como motor de inovação. O entrelaçamento entre memória coletiva e práticas contemporâneas permite imaginar futuros mais inclusivos e sustentáveis, nos quais o interior não é entendido em oposição ao urbano, mas como território complementar, capaz de propor soluções únicas. A UBI, Universidade da Beira Interior, pode, portanto, atuar como eixo articulador entre a tradição têxtil, a educação superior e as redes globais de inovação, a colaborar com o desenvolvimento do polo criativo e científico da região, destacando a Covilhã.

Assim, o texto discorre sobre o planejamento e a criação de um observatório de futuros com foco no interior de Portugal e suas heranças culturais, industriais e relações transfronteiriças como base para a análise e projeção de futuros possíveis. O documento apresenta uma revisão bibliográfica pontual, com autores que abordam inovação, economia circular, noções de território e futuros, além daqueles que tratam de metodologias de projeto em Design. Por fim, analisa o potencial e a viabilidade deste observatório, destacando características como resiliência cultural e demandas econômicas contemporâneas, sendo agentes de transformação apoiados pelo Design em soluções criativas e inovativas para enfrentar os desafios atuais e futuros.

Reading the Algorithmic Zeitgeist: Trend Studies as a Compass for the AI–Journalism Nexus

Ana Marta M. Flores

This work explores how trend analysis methods can be applied to decode the evolving relationship between Artificial Intelligence (AI) and journalism. Drawing from contemporary cultural diagnostics, the study identifies interlinked trends that reflect the ethical, emotional and epistemic turbulence surrounding technological transformation in media ecosystems. *The Age of Post-Trust*, examines how AI intensifies the ongoing crisis of credibility, accelerating a transition from institutional authority to algorithmic mediation. *The Paradox of Efficiency*, maps the tension between promised productivity and the human cost of over-automation — where speed and scale coexist with editorial fatigue and epistemic erosion. *Alpha + Ctrl+Z Audiences*, traces the cultural codes of Gen Z and Gen Alpha, whose attention economies and aesthetic logics reshape notions of truth, literacy and belonging. And, *The Syndrome of Technosalvation* problematises the belief in AI as a universal fix for systemic crises — a modern myth that conflates technological progress with moral or social advancement. By combining tools from trend studies, media sociology and cultural semiotics, this research proposes a framework to understand AI not merely as a tool, but as a cultural force that reconfigures epistemic norms, emotional economies and journalistic practice. The analysis contributes to broader reflections on how media organisations can cultivate critical literacy, ethical foresight and narrative resilience in an age when credibility itself becomes a contested terrain.

Tradition and emergent technologies: AI's Role in Contemporary Arts & Crafts

André Matos

The relationship between art, science and technology is historically complex and has been evolving over time. Over the last years we've seen the gradual introduction of new forms and tools for creation, and that has a natural impact in the type of art that is produced and how it is perceived and apprehended. This emergence of AI has revolutionized the creation of art, not only by replacing much of the repetitive manual work, but also by improving the quality and speed of production. We have seen artists and researchers working with new deep learning models to explore the greater potential of AI, but also numerous discussions about the development of these technologies and the different labor and ethical challenges they pose. How is this rapid technological revolution being perceived by those who work primarily with creating art with their own hands? Should there be a concern about becoming obsolete in the face of these changes? The aim of this project is to provide an overview of existing academic knowledge on the role of artificial intelligence in the different areas of arts and crafts and to explore how AI can coexist and be used to amplify the creative process of artisanal work.

When Culture Moves: Cultural Motion and the Global Commodification of Indian Practices

Archisha Mazumdar, Krishnapriya T K

Yoga and Ayurveda, historically embedded within Indian spiritual and community life, have undergone a profound transformation in the way they are being perceived globally recently. What were once practiced as systematic practices of health and philosophy, are now getting reconstituted within wellness communities as commodified lifestyle markers — from yoga mats at studios to turmeric lattes and branded supplements. We aim to situate such shifts within broader dynamics of cultural translation, commodification, and trend diffusion, examining how practices rooted in local culture and history are rebranded as global consumer goods or lifestyle products.

Beyond wellness, similar trajectories are also evident in contemporary fashion and lifestyle markets. The “clean girl” aesthetic popularised hair oiling as a beauty trend detached from its South Asian lineage; henna resurfaced at festivals such as Coachella as a decorative accessory; Italian luxury house Prada launched slippers that looked identical to the humble Indian kolhapuris; and Reformation’s marketing of the dupatta as a “Scandinavian scarf” provoked digital backlash led by South Asian influencers. Even daily artefacts, such as Indian leaf plates, are increasingly repositioned as eco-design commodities within Western markets.

This presentation aims to analyse how traditions become “culture in motion” — circulating through global consumerism, reconfigured within trend cycles, and negotiated within online publics. It highlights the tensions between heritage, identity, and market logics, asking: what is lost, what is reimagined, and who profits when culture sells?

The Cry of the Whales: Sociosemiotic Analysis of More-than-Human Agency in Platformized Climate Activism

Beatriz de Urquijo Isoard

Despite the accelerating climate crisis, fossil fuel megaprojects continue expanding. Traditional anthropocentric frameworks of climate justice activism inadequately represent affected non-human species' interests. The Saguaro Project in the Gulf of California exemplifies this tension: infrastructure to export liquefied natural gas from the U.S. Permian Basin to Asia via Mexico's Pacific coastline faces opposition due to severe environmental and ecological risks threatening whale populations and marine biodiversity. Within increasingly platformized and mediatized societies, a critical question emerges: how can more-than-human entities claim agency and voice in digital public spheres to defend their own existence? Previous scholarship has examined digital environmental activism (Buhre, 2023, 2025; Hjorth et al., 2016), mediatized social movements leveraging digital affordances (Bonini & Treré, 2024), and online environmental discourse strategies (Amondarain et al., 2022). However, existing research predominantly focuses on human activists speaking for nature or legal frameworks granting rights to nature, maintaining anthropocentric mediation (García-Orellana et al., 2025). Limited analysis exists on how platforms enable semiotic construction of direct more-than-human agency—positioning non-human entities as active discourse-producing subjects. Sociosemiotic approaches examining production conditions of these “voiced” non-human claims in platformized environments remain underdeveloped (Bolin, 2024; Carlón, 2024). This research conducts sociosemiotic analysis, grounded in Eliseo Verón's social discourse theory, of the campaign “Las Ballenas Demandan” (The Whales Sue), where Gulf of California whales are positioned as legal subjects suing against fossil fuel expansion. The study examines how Nuestro Futuro A.C. constructs discursive conditions enabling whales to

"raise their voice" through songs, presence, and claimed agency on Instagram. Analysis focuses on production, circulation, and recognition of more-than-human discourses, investigating how platformized mediatization enables interspecies political subjectivity bridging online symbolic activism and offline legal-material interventions, offering methodological approaches for analyzing climate activism's anticipatory narratives challenging anthropocentric paradigms.

Narrative-Based, Multidirectional Trends

Claire Haas

This presentation presents a narrative-based, multidirectional model of trends, underpinned by Cultural Studies theories, representing a new articulation of cultural and trends theories. Reexamining the DNA of a trend, this model suggests that trends consist of mindset narratives (invisible plane) and narrative expressions through language and cultural objects (visible plane), based in the narrative theory of thought (Beach, 2016). It roots the process translation in the cultural communication model (Grossberg, 2006; Williams, 1961), arguing that how translation happens in any given observer is dependent on their cultural context and its accompanying shared meanings, necessarily producing a plurality of different connotative means from any given cultural object (Hall, 1973, 2012). Because the same cultural objects impact mindset narratives in multiple ways, there exists multidirectional cultural movement, simultaneously going in a variety of directions, that is inherently related, suggesting that a trend is inherently multidirectional. This challenges established frameworks in Trend Studies that describe trends as vectoral, moving in a particular direction with a start and end point (Dragt, 2017; Powers, 2019; Raymond, 2019; Vejlgaard, 2008), aligned with the Enlightenment idea of progress, or what Devon Powers calls "proactive optimism" (Eagleton, 2000; Powers, 2019, pp. 119–120). This model suggests a definition of a sociocultural trend as a cluster of shared cultural narratives which can be observed in representations (cultural objects and expressed narratives) and argues that understanding the whole of our zeitgeist requires a plural understanding of cultural

movement. Because it is based in Cultural Studies core texts, this model strengthens the argument for Trends Studies to continue as an approach of the cultural management subdiscipline within Cultural Studies.

Singing the Sensitive in the Age of Algorithms: Building Laufey's Fandom Through Streaming Platforms

Fátima Meléndez Gómez

This qualitative research examines Laufey's fandom through the analysis of comments posted on YouTube Music. The aim is to understand how the "Lauvers," a transnational fan community, use comment sections as forms of emotional activism, sharing feelings and personal experiences that go beyond individual listening. Preliminary findings show that these comments foster community, reframe the artist's music, and consolidate a collective identity in virtual spaces. Thus, comment sections on streaming platforms not only accompany music consumption but also function as performative spaces where fans transform listening into cultural and affective practices. The case of Laufey demonstrates how digital fandoms are not passive consumers but active agents in meaning-making and community building. This research contributes to communication, digital culture, and music studies by highlighting how fandoms create emotional communities within streaming platforms.

James Bond – 007 a marca que nunca passa de Moda

Filipa Moreira

Esta comunicação tem como objectivo apresentar a marca James Bond – 007 e do seu produto, bem como identificar quais os componente estruturais da narrativa dos filmes de James Bond que se relacionam com a realidade que envolve cada produção. Além de acompanhar/analisar a transformação da personagem literária numa produção cinematográfica de entretenimento global. Os filmes de 007 criaram uma marca forte e diferenciada na indústria do entretenimento mundial, distinguindo-se pela sua constante inovação, pela sua estrutura fílmica única, e pela forte relação que as suas narrativas criam com a realidade que as envolve. A aplicação das técnicas de product placement no cinema (Galician & Bordeau, 2004) (verbal/hand placement, implied endorsement, signage, ou clutter product placement) em determinados elementos narrativos contribuiu para a longevidade e sucesso da marca James Bond – 007, assim como das marcas/produtos parceiros que beneficiam claramente da associação a símbolos/significados relacionados com a cultura Bond e da construção de narrativas comerciais inovadoras. Os argumentos dos filmes de Bond acompanham acontecimentos históricos marcantes, sendo que as marcas que surgem retratadas nestas produções (através da aplicação das técnicas de product placement) permitem fazer uma abordagem social/comercial do período em que cada um dos filmes foi produzido. Esta comunicação pretende, assim, explorar as diversas potencialidades que este franchise cinematográfico tem enquanto eficaz plataforma de promoção e comunicação de marcas e produtos, uma vez que, a cada nova produção cinematográfica a marca James Bond – 007 se torna mais apelativa/desejada para estabelecer parcerias comerciais graças aos seus recursos de comunicação inatos e a uma identidade forte no mercado de consumo e de entretenimento, pois cada um dos diferentes argumentos espelha mudanças sociais, acções políticas, práticas culturais e hábitos de consumo.

Powerful Storytelling in the AI Era

Gemma Vallet

In an age where algorithms generate content at scale and AI floods our feeds with hallucinative narratives, how can brands, creators, and educators ensure stories remain meaningful, ethical, and human? Dr. Gemma Vallet explores the tension between automation and authenticity, showing how contemporary methodologies can activate storytelling that is not only powerful but also aligned with sustainable values. Drawing on her work with global brands and the BSBI Future Lab, she makes the case for rethinking storytelling as a cultural and activist act—one that cuts through digital noise, resists shallow narratives, and reclaims AI as a tool for shaping stories that inspire, mobilize, and endure.

Trends on Websummit 2025

Illa Branco

This communication examines the convergence of cultural, creative and technological signals emerging around one of the most important tech events in the world: Web Summit 2025. The focus is discussed on how new tools, experimental products and early-stage technological developments indicate shifts in behaviour, creative practices and digital participation within contemporary society. Drawing on an exploratory ethnographic approach, the analysis identifies initial trend signals related to AI-mediated creativity, new modes of interaction in digital environments, and evolving patterns of content production and consumption. The aim of this communication is to outline the directions suggested by these signals identified in the event and to provide a framework for understanding how technological contemporary change intersects with culture and creative work in the present context.

Macrotendências e Política: Compreender a Representação LGBTQIA+ no Policymaking

João Miguel Abreu Miranda

Num contexto de crescente polarização política e de intensas transformações sociais, a utilização da análise de tendências para além da lógica de mercado e consumo torna-se cada vez mais relevante. Esta investigação explora de que forma os Estudos de Tendências, tradicionalmente associados ao comportamento do consumidor e à previsão cultural, podem ser estrategicamente aplicados ao campo político, especificamente à análise das identidades LGBTQIA+ e da sua representação no processo de policy making. Ao combinar Estudos de Tendências, Estudos Culturais e Ciência Política, esta investigação adota uma abordagem interdisciplinar para compreender como padrões culturais emergentes moldam a comunicação política e as políticas identitárias. Metodologicamente, o estudo estrutura-se através da triangulação cultural, combinando desk research, coolhunting e entrevistas semi-estruturadas com especialistas e early adopters da comunidade LGBTQIA+. Os resultados revelam um cenário paradoxal: embora as identidades queer tenham maior visibilidade nos meios de comunicação e no espaço digital, a representação política mantém-se frágil e os movimentos extremistas ganham força. A metodologia de coolhunting, adaptada para análise política, demonstrou ser uma ferramenta eficaz para identificar e mapear sinais com impacto político, social e simbólico. Através das macrotendências, estes sinais foram sistematizados e transformados em insights estratégicos e recomendações legislativas orientadas para políticas mais inclusivas e representativas. Esta investigação demonstra que os Estudos de Tendências podem ser uma ferramenta valiosa para a comunicação política e para o desenho de políticas públicas. Ao antecipar mentalidades e mudanças culturais, as instituições podem reforçar o envolvimento democrático e desenvolver estratégias que respondam a aspirações emergentes e riscos sociais. Este trabalho propõe, assim, uma nova forma de pensar a relação entre cultura, política e comunicação no século XXI.

Mirrored rhetoric and cyclical monologues: Social media, trends, and algorithmic structuring of online messages

Julianna Kirschner

Social media is already an important form of engagement in today's communication landscape. People with all different forms of experience—from social media researchers and professionals to regular users—should be aware of the cultural and social trends that have come from the use of these technologies. This presentation will shed light on the origins of social media, the evolution of these platforms in response to market demands (perceived and otherwise), and the changed way in which we communicate within such spaces. The aforementioned changes primarily have shifted to an audience of one—the user themselves.

Challenges and Strategies for Implementing Trend Methodologies in Organizations

Juliano Lira Guzzo, Romário Vieira Souza

In the era of digital acceleration, an organization's ability to anticipate and respond to emerging patterns is a crucial competitive advantage. However, implementing trend methodologies and technologies transcends the mere adoption of tools, proving to be a complex and multifaceted process. Drawing from a systematic literature review of 16 ScienceDirect publications, this presentation offers a critical analysis of the key challenges and a compendium of best practices for the strategic and successful integration of foresight within the corporate environment. The analysis explores the multifaceted obstacles that compromise these initiatives, which are rarely purely technical. It delves into organizational and cultural challenges, such as resistance to change and internal skill gaps; technological and data challenges, including issues of quality, integration, and the deepening of the digital divide; and ethical and governance imperatives, such as the need for transparency and trustworthiness in AI systems. In response, this work synthesizes a set of strategies and best practices to overcome such barriers. It proposes using structured frameworks, like the Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE) model, to guide technological adoption. It highlights the importance of a human-centric and socio-technical focus, aligned with the principles of Industry 5.0, that prioritizes organizational learning and skill development. Finally, it underscores the need to cultivate dynamic and digital capabilities as a key element for transforming trend data into tangible strategic value. The conclusion is that success lies not in the technology itself but in a holistic approach that harmonizes strategy, culture, and technology, offering a roadmap for organizations to convert foresight into action.

Trends and Digital Humanities: Emerging Pathways for Fashion through Artificial Intelligence and 3D Simulation

Macivaldo Santana dos Santos

The development of digital visual artifacts in fashion and clothing is closely tied to macro-level cultural and behavioral trends. Despite the growing emphasis on artificial intelligence (AI) and 3D technologies in trend reports, there remains a lack of studies that connect technological innovation with social representativeness. This study investigates how digital tools, particularly AI and 3D simulation, can be applied to fashion from the perspective of digital humanities. The research adopts an applied and qualitative approach, combining literature review with the analysis of practical uses of digital tools for image generation, identified through a structured questionnaire. The focus is on constructing more humanized and equitable representations that address gender, racial, and body diversity. Findings suggest that human agency—sensitive and strategically engaged—enhances interaction with digital systems, guiding prompts and commands that lead to more inclusive visual outcomes. The results also highlight the dual role of AI in fashion: on one hand, it amplifies creative possibilities by optimizing workflows and enabling aesthetic experimentation; on the other, it raises ethical challenges related to algorithmic bias and exclusion of marginalized groups. By framing these dynamics through the lens of digital humanities, the study positions human–machine interaction as a critical site for negotiating inclusivity and representation in digital fashion. As a contribution, it expands fashion’s visual repertoire, strengthens representative practices in the collective mindset, and provides insights for the training of professionals attuned to ongoing digital transformations. This research thus underscores the importance of combining innovation with social responsibility, situating digital fashion practices within broader debates on technology, culture, and equity.

Futourism em Portugal: Vanguarda, Culpa ou Negócio de Branding Cultural?

Manuel Pinto Grunfeld

Entre transformações culturais, urgências ecológicas e tensões de mercado, o turismo projeta-se como laboratório de tendências. A noção de futourism surge como proposta para repensar o turismo em chave de sustentabilidade e digitalização, atuando como categoria que traduz a urgência ecológica em discurso turístico, promovida pela União Europeia (European Commission, 2023–2026), e que a marca de destino Portugal apropriou-se na campanha It's not tourism. It's futourism (2023). Mais do que um slogan, foi apresentada como manifesto de doze propósitos de Ano Novo 2024 —enquadrados na Estratégia de Turismo 2027— para inspirar viagens conscientes e responsáveis, cruzando fatores éticos, políticos e de mercado. Conceptualmente, seguindo Powers (2025), Raymond (2010) e Vejlgard (2008), a tendência entende-se como padrão dinâmico de mudança cultural e comunicacional. Acrescenta-se a noção de branding cultural de Holt (2004) e os contributos de autores como Anholt (2010), Dinnie (2022) e Kotler et al. (2022), que sublinham como as marcas de destino operam como narrativas coletivas que encarnam tensões e mitos culturais. O caso português interpreta-se em três camadas, articuladas com o Mapa de Tendências do Trends and Culture Management Lab (2025): (i) vanguarda, como apropriação da macrotendência Redesenho dos Estilos de Vida, onde crises recentes impulsionaram mudanças em práticas e valores rumo à resiliência e ao bem-estar; (ii) culpa, em resposta aos impactos do turismo massivo, vinculada à macrotendência Narrativas Ancoradas, que descreve a reutilização de relatos simbólicos para compensar memórias fragmentadas; e (iii) negócio, como estratégia de reposicionamento vinculada à macrotendência Washing do Sustentável, que alerta para discursos de sustentabilidade com baixo impacto real. Em conjunto, a comunicação do futourism português condensa inovação, reparação e mercantilização num mesmo

relato, exemplificando como tendências globais se traduzem em narrativas culturais e como a comunicação turística se converte em campo de disputa sobre o futuro.

Contribuições semióticas para o estudo das relações entre consumo e tendências

Matheus da Silva Duarte

A hiper mediatização da rotina dos indivíduos transforma a natureza da sua percepção, sobre o ato de consumir, de um caráter de desejo para o de necessidade. Um dos fatores de maior impacto no processo de construção de hábitos de consumo são as tendências, definidas por Powers (2025) como padrões dinâmicos de mudança observável. Sendo assim, é evidente que para compreender a influência das tendências na sociedade é necessário decodificar os sistemas de construção de significado que levam à repetição desses padrões, permeando assim os domínios da semiótica. Dentre as diversas ferramentas de análise do significado, o percurso gerativo de sentido, proposto por Julien Greimas e apresentado por Fiorin (2013), proporciona uma sistematização da construção de sentido, partindo do campo mais subjetivo e intangível, até uma representação mais visual e tangível. De forma semelhante, Henrik Vejlgard (2008) aborda as relações entre tendências e os hábitos dos consumidores, apresentando através de um diagrama a ideia de que em um mesmo cenário compartilhado, enquanto um grupo, denominado Trendsetters, possui acesso a um conjunto vasto de manifestações e significados, um outro, os Mainstreamers, recebe apenas uma parcela reduzida e manipulada do mesmo conteúdo. Assim, partindo da premissa de que ambos os autores abordam o processo de sistematização da construção de significado, o presente estudo propõe um diagrama que atue como mediador entre as visões e facilite a compreensão do processo de dispersão do sentido ao longo do processo de consumo das manifestações das tendências, partindo de um ponto de maior complexidade para um de menor complexidade.

Tensões entre a perspectiva decolonial indígena e o conceito de ‘novo’ na moda e nos estudos de tendências

Miruna Raimundi de Gois, Daniela Novelli

O objetivo é discutir teoricamente a relação entre os estudos de tendências, historicamente ancorados em metodologias eurocentradas, e as perspectivas decoloniais indígenas no campo da moda. A pesquisa parte do problema de que as tendências culturais, ao seguirem o sistema de moda ancorado nas novidades, acabam perpetuando práticas que marginalizam povos tradicionais, considerados como ‘não moda’. Isso revela o viés colonial que exclui povos originários tanto como criadores quanto como consumidores legítimos de tendências. A metodologia adotada é de caráter qualitativo e bibliográfico, a partir de leituras e análise crítica de autores que discutem os estudos de tendências, sistema da moda e moda indígena. O estudo articula também conceitos dos Estudos de Tendências e dos Estudos Culturais, buscando tensionar a noção de efemeridade/novidade no Sistema da Moda e por conseguinte nos relatórios de tendências, com a ideia de “cultura lenta” (McCracken, 2011), que aproxima-se das práticas ancestrais dos povos indígenas. Os resultados apontam que o Sistema da Moda, ao legitimar apenas centros euro-norte-americanos como criadores de tendências, reforça hierarquias coloniais que renegam as culturas tradicionais a objetos estéticos ou exóticos, esvaído de significados. Em contrapartida, a moda indígena, compreendida como práticas de adornar o corpo e expressar identidades culturais, atua como campo de re-existência, desafiando as estruturas coloniais. Se a moda vive da expectativa do novo, mas se organiza em ciclos temporais-sazonais, o que de fato define a novidade? Não seria apenas mais do mesmo em atualizações estéticas diferentes? Nesse sentido, por que as culturas tradicionais, com seus

saberes e cosmovisões, não são reconhecidas como criadoras de tendências, mas apenas como inspiração ou apropriação estética-cultural? A pesquisa demonstra-se embrionária e aponta como possibilidade a articulação entre pensamento decolonial indígena e estudos de tendências que permite ampliar o campo.

The fall of Trend Reports as a strategic instrument of cultural analysis and communication: reflection on possible solutions.

Nelson Pinheiro Gomes

Trend reports have been, for the past decades, one of the main results and outputs of trend networks and associated consultancy institutions. They are important to show the trend analysis results of the team, to bring in new business, to map cultural change, and to refine research, systematization and insight generation processes. However, something was lost along the way and several problems arise: businesses complain about the time and resources needed to review, study and implement the information of the reports; the reports have become growingly generic and they have been losing their insights, their impactful nature; also, the pressure to produce reports every year is making them redundant, highlighting mostly what has been our reality for years. We have to ask, have they lost their original purpose? In this communication, we openly address this question, adding to the growing dialogue about the status and objectives of trend reports in the market and in the scientific environment.

Práticas culturais e indivíduos modernos: relações entre consumo e identidade LGBTI+

Nicolas Santos Nunes

Falar em contemporaneidade é reconhecer um espaço-tempo onde culturas se interconectam, identidades se reconfiguram e tendências operam como sinais de mudança social. Partindo do pressuposto de que as relações de construção identitárias e sociais são materializadas pelo 'consumo enquanto rito' (Perez, 2020), pode-se afirmar que as dinâmicas entre os indivíduos e os objetos-marca se complexifica em nível de inferência em suas práticas culturais e valores compartilhados (Hall, 1997), deslocando, em alguma medida, suas próprias visões de mundo. Essas relações, que navegam entre o individual e o coletivo, são diretamente atravessadas pelas tendências, que servem como pontos de identificação de mudança e transformação (Powers, 2019). Em uma relação ainda mais aprofundada, este consumo um ganha outro nível semântico atrelado ao consumo politizado (Echegaray, 2012), crítico em seus valores de ética ambiental e social, principalmente ligado às minorias sociais marginalizadas, como a comunidade LGBTI+. Assim, entender os processos de construção de sentido e prospectar um método para análise cultural a partir do atravessamento das tendências culturais e de LGBTI+'s pode não apenas fornecer informações valiosas para um mapeamento etnográfico destes indivíduos, como também auxiliar estratégias de marcas que desejam produzir visualidade, objetos e/ou serviços mais responsáveis e que permitam produções de 'ser' próprias dos indivíduos (Arvidsson, 2005). Logo, o presente trabalho propõe um diagrama-método aberto, pensado como uma ferramenta analítica para a visualização e identificação da complexidade das relações objeto-marca x minorias sociais, através de elementos culturais, entendendo que as tendências permeiam esses processos como elementos elaboradores de visões de mundo.

AI-Generated Cinema and the Future of Cultural Criticism

Sofía Alvarez Salas

The rise of generative artificial intelligence has begun to reshape not only the production of images and narratives, but also the cultural frameworks through which cinema is created, circulated, and evaluated. From text-to-image software to fully AI-generated short films, these tools introduce new questions about authorship, authenticity, and artistic labor. While debates around automation and creativity often focus on technical novelty, less attention has been paid to how such technologies transform the critical and curatorial practices that determine cultural visibility and value. This presentation explores how AI-generated images and narratives are entering film culture, and how their presence challenges the role of critics, festivals, and curators as mediators of meaning. Drawing on my professional experience as a film critic and juror in international festivals (Berlinale Forum, Brussels IFF, Lima, AI Este), I analyze how evaluative frameworks are adapting—or resisting—these disruptions. The case of Spanish-language cinema, often marginalized within European cultural hierarchies, provides a fertile lens: here, the negotiation between human creativity, machine-generated content, and critical discourse becomes especially visible. By situating cinema within broader “algorithmic cultures,” I argue that criticism itself can be understood as a form of cultural trend research: mapping signals of change in how societies perceive reality, authorship, and the moving image. Ultimately, this work highlights both the risks of homogenization and the potential for inclusive innovation in rethinking what counts as cinema and cultural production in the age of AI.

Indigenous Wellness Trends: Mediated Representations of Ayurveda in India

Subin Paul

Although science communication is a robust and burgeoning area of academic inquiry, it continues to lack scholarship on alternative sciences, such as the South Asian system of healing called Ayurveda (“knowledge of life”). This presentation seeks to address this problem by studying Ayurveda from a journalistic and cultural perspective. Ayurveda is slowly emerging as an international wellness trend while remaining an everyday medical choice for millions of people in South Asia. In fact, within the South Asian context, the consumption of Ayurveda is culturally associated with “a wholesome lifestyle and ecological awareness” (Bode, 2006). Drawing on postcolonial theorist Gayatri Spivak’s conceptualization of representation, I critically review the media coverage of Ayurveda in *The Wire Science*, a science news portal based in India. This study unravels the fractured and ambivalent nature of Ayurveda’s representation, which I suspect to be an upshot of *The Wire Science*’s inherent efforts to neutralize neocolonial and nationalist narratives surrounding Ayurveda in India. *The Wire Science* functions not only as a vector of science communication but also as a discursive site where the boundaries of science and culture are negotiated. I argue that, in addition to accuracy and verification, science news must reckon with colonial histories, as these shape what counts as science in today’s globalizing world. This presentation thus contributes to ongoing conversations in media and communication studies about the appropriation of cultural products (e.g., Shome, 2014; Vats, 2016) and moves beyond biomedical science and Global North media, which have come to define scholarship on science news within the field of communication.

Forever Twilight in Forks: Vinte Anos de Fandom e Cultura Participativa

Susana Samagaia Garcia da Silva e Sandra Rech

As pesquisas sobre o comportamento dos fãs iniciam a partir dos anos 1990, e o fandom, constitui-se em uma subcultura de consumo, autêntica, em que os integrantes se relacionam socialmente (Santos, 2019). O fandom da Saga Crepúsculo tornou-se popular em paralelo ao uso das redes sociais (Biasi, 2024), potencializando a participação de fãs multigeracionais. Assim, apresenta-se o evento Forever Twilight in Forks, que ocorre anualmente desde 2006, no mês de setembro, e celebrou em 2025, 20 anos da Saga. Por meio de pesquisa bibliográfica e netnográfica, acompanhou-se a cobertura do evento e a produção de conteúdo no perfil da influenciadora brasileira convidada (@malizialu). A pesquisa resulta na descrição do evento deste ano, que comumente fornece aos fãs experiências imersivas e participativas – gratuitas e pagas – como sessão de autógrafos, concurso de cosplay, comidas inspiradas nos livros, festas e fotos. O evento contou com a participação da autora da série de livros que fez sucesso no cinema, Stephanie Meyer, e dos atores Kellan Lutz e Peter Facinelli. Conforme a influenciadora, a autora confirmou a continuidade da produção das graphics novels, comentou novos rumos para a personagem, Leah, e revelou detalhes sobre a série animada de Midnight Sun em produção pela Netflix com lançamento até 2030. Cita que o roteiro já foi finalizado, e que estão na parte artística e inspirou-se no Aranhaverso – tendo inclusive apresentado duas artes conceituais da série para os presentes, solicitados a não registrar o momento. Coleman (2019) destaca que o festival capitalizou o desejo dos fãs e promove a celebração do fandom da Saga bem como fortaleceu a economia de Forks. Com isso, afirma-se que o fandom como cultura participativa envolve a experiência coletiva, a partir do conteúdo de mídia de massa, dentro de uma comunidade que se une em torno de paixões e interesses compartilhados (Jenkins, 2018).

Tech Keynotes as Performative Spaces: Mapping the Spectacle-Driven Diffusion of Innovations

Suzana Cohen

This communication analyses how Tech Keynotes and similar events function as performative spaces to actively mediate and accelerate the diffusion of technological trends and innovations. We argue that the success of modern innovations is increasingly tied to spectacle-driven engagement and strategic narrative control within these key digital moments. The presentation will operationalise a comprehensive theoretical architecture, extending Cohen's research (2020, 2021). We detail two core, interconnected models: 1) The Technology Trend Pathway: This framework maps the complete evolutionary journey of a trend, from intangible cultural mindsets (the ideological context) through the stages of product development to the eventual creation of market-ready technological artifacts; 2) The Layered S-Curve Model: This novel model integrates the diffusion of the underlying cultural mindsets with the traditional S-curve of innovation adoption, revealing how the former is used to leverage and accelerate the latter. The presentation will also revisit some of the technology trends mapped by Cohen (2020), such as the Acting of Oz and The Spectacular Circuit, which happen to be regularly interconnected in tech keynotes. Using high-profile, mediated events such as Meta's Connect 2025 and Tesla's We, Robot (2024) as empirical case studies, we will demonstrate how the strategic convergence of cultural trends, managed spectacle, and the unveiling of products actively reshapes public perception. The analysis reveals a potent mechanism linking the art of digital performance directly to the increased visibility and accelerated acceptance of emerging technologies. This research offers insights for those seeking to understand the dynamics of accelerated innovation.

Between Tradition and Transformation: Media in Bhutan and the Negotiation of Global Trends

Szymon Zylinski

Bhutanese media occupy a unique position within the global landscape, situated between a strong cultural imperative to safeguard national identity and an increasing exposure to global media trends. This tension is rooted in Bhutan's relatively recent adoption of television and the internet in 1999, followed by a rapid digital transformation that continues to reshape its communicative environment. On the one hand, Bhutanese media actors—journalists, regulators, and cultural stakeholders—emphasize the role of media as guardians of tradition, language, and Gross National Happiness, reinforcing continuity and cultural preservation. Public broadcasters, in particular, foreground narratives of national unity and heritage, seeking to resist the homogenizing influence of globalized content. On the other hand, younger audiences and independent outlets increasingly engage with international platforms such as Facebook, TikTok, and YouTube, adopting new genres, visual styles, and modes of interaction that align Bhutan with wider transnational flows of culture and information. The resulting media ecology is characterized by ambivalence: aspirations to modernize coexist with concerns over cultural erosion, and global formats are often selectively appropriated and indigenized. For instance, the professionalization of journalism draws on global standards of ethics and digital innovation, yet remains shaped by local hierarchies and sociopolitical sensitivities. Similarly, the vibrant use of social media enables grassroots expression, but raises anxieties over misinformation and threats to social cohesion. This paper explores these contradictions, conceptualizing Bhutanese media as a field negotiating between stability and change, tradition and modernity. It argues that Bhutan exemplifies how smaller media systems in the Global South articulate their own pathways to modernization, not simply by mimicking dominant models, but by adapting them within cultural frameworks that privilege continuity. The

analysis provides insight into the dynamics of media globalization, showing how Bhutan mediates its desire to remain distinctly itself while simultaneously aspiring to participate in a shared global media culture.

From climate misinformation to futures literacy: rethinking communication in the age of cultural uncertainty

Tamara Natale de Moraes

In an era marked by digital acceleration and media convergence, misinformation has become one of the greatest challenges for communication and cultural understanding. Among its most harmful forms, climate misinformation distorts public perception of the environmental crisis, fuels denialist narratives, and hinders collective action. This paper investigates how climate misinformation operates as a cultural phenomenon - produced, circulated, and legitimized within digital platforms and media ecosystems that combine entertainment, ideology, politics, and algorithmic amplification. Drawing on discourse analysis, the research examines how these narratives are mediated by platforms and shape imaginaries of the future, influencing public engagement with sustainability. As a counterpoint, the paper introduces the concept of Futures Literacy, as formulated by UNESCO, as a communicational and educational strategy capable of expanding the collective capacity to imagine alternative futures and critically engage with informational flows. Through the analysis of media content, platform dynamics, and participatory educational practices, the study discusses how futures literacy can strengthen resilience against misinformation and promote new cultural competencies for the climate transition. In summary, the paper argues that the intersection between communication, new media, and futures literacy provides a powerful framework for rethinking the role of cultural trends and digital platforms in shaping collective agency and

anticipating ongoing transformations. Understanding and transforming the narratives that sustain climate misinformation is, therefore, more than a matter of fact-checking - it involves cultivating a literacy of futures that enables us to critically inhabit a world in motion.

Vestuário esportivo como mídia: atletas-ícones na construção estética do tênis feminino

Thaissa Schneider

O tênis feminino, desde o final do século XIX, configurou-se como espaço de rupturas estéticas e culturais, no qual a indumentária ultrapassa a função técnica e se insere em disputas simbólicas de gênero, identidade e estilo. De Maud Watson e Suzanne Lenglen, que desafiaram convenções com vestidos mais leves, a Gertrude Moran e Ann White, que escandalizaram com rendas e catsuits, a história da moda no tênis revela um campo de tensão constante entre tradição e inovação. Neste contexto, o presente estudo analisa, por meio de abordagem qualitativa e de estudo de caso, como as atletas Serena Williams e Naomi Osaka, patrocinadas pela Nike, utilizam seus uniformes em competições para articular performance, estilo e comunicação cultural. A coleta de dados envolveu revisão bibliográfica, levantamento documental e análise midiática de campanhas, reportagens e imagens que registram episódios emblemáticos, como o catsuit preto de Serena no Roland Garros de 2018 e o uniforme em parceria com a Ambush usado por Osaka no US Open de 2024. A análise permitiu compreender como esses uniformes se tornaram dispositivos de expressão identitária e de difusão de tendências. Os resultados apontam que a Nike desempenha papel central como mediadora entre esporte e moda, transformando o uniforme esportivo em produto midiático e simbólico de consumo. As trajetórias de

Serena Williams e Naomi Osaka demonstram como, na contemporaneidade, o tênis feminino se consolidou como palco de experimentação estética, capaz de influenciar não apenas o universo esportivo, mas também a cultura de moda. Assim, este estudo contribui para o campo das pesquisas em tendências ao evidenciar como o vestuário esportivo, ao ser apropriado por atletas-ícones, extrapola a quadra e se afirma como linguagem cultural e estética em escala global.

From Metrosexual to Mainstream: The Evolution of Male Grooming Advertising in Indian Media'

Twinkle Soni

This paper traces the evolution of male grooming advertising in India over the last two decades. Using content analysis of television, print, and digital advertisements, it examines shifts in masculine imagery, messaging tone, and gender representation. Drawing from gender theory and media discourse analysis, the study explores how the notion of “metrosexuality” transitioned to mainstream male identity and whether this evolution has helped reduce the gender gap in beauty and personal care advertising. Findings reveal a gradual shift from hyper-masculine portrayals to more inclusive, emotional, and aesthetic appeals targeting Indian men. The study suggests that although strides have been made in diversifying male representation, residual gender biases persist in the framing and positioning of grooming content. In this paper, we will highlight how the gap in projecting males is still stagnating. The customers are responsible for accepting such a perspective, or the advertisers in building that Prospect.

A tensão cultural enquanto unidade semiótica: contributos para uma epistemologia cultural das tendências

William Cantú

Esta comunicação propõe a tensão cultural como categoria epistemológica para compreender o funcionamento das tendências culturais e procura contribuir para uma leitura hermenêutica das tendências. Partindo da semiótica da cultura (Lotman, 1989) e das recentes contribuições dos Estudos de Tendências (Gomes et al. 2021; Cantú & Gomes, 2024; Powers, 2025), as tendências são entendidas como processos simbólicos de mediação entre o instituído e o emergente, revelando as fricções e negociações de sentido que estruturam a cultura. A tensão cultural designa o espaço hermenêutico em que diferentes sistemas de valor, linguagem e imaginação coletiva se confrontam e se traduzem mutuamente, constituindo o centro das transformações socioculturais. Enquanto dispositivo epistemológico, esta tensão permite observar como a mudança opera nas margens da semiosfera, onde novos códigos e significados se formam e se estabilizam (Lotman, 1988, 1989). Essa fricção simbólica, longe de representar apenas um conflito simbólico, manifesta a vitalidade do campo cultural onde as tendências se formam. No contexto dos Estudos de Tendências, tal conceito reconfigura a investigação da cultura enquanto exercício interpretativo, não apenas contribuindo para a identificação de sinais emergentes, mas para reforçando a importância da análise das forças semióticas que os sustentam. Propõe-se, assim, uma hermenêutica das tendências assente na leitura das tensões culturais como indicadores de mudança e instrumentos de compreensão

das dinâmicas simbólicas do presente. A articulação entre semiótica (Santaella, 2008; Chandler, 2017), cultura e tendências (Gomes e Cantú, 2023; Dragt, 2023) converte-se num dispositivo crítico e operacional, que opera como um toolkit capaz de transformar a leitura cultural em prática criativa e de intervenção situada, que une imaginação e intervenção Cultural.

Integrating Strategic Foresight into Technology Roadmapping

Wilson Silva Prata, Juliano Lira Guzzo

Conventional strategic instruments frequently struggle to maintain their usefulness in a world shaped by constant transformation and digital acceleration. Technological Roadmaps (TRMs) are essential for aligning technology with business strategy, but their traditional, linear nature can create blind spots to disruptive changes, particularly in a dynamic environment such as our current era - a world in constant motion. This rigidity requires frequent, resource-intensive updates to maintain relevance. This presentation directly addresses the challenge of how organizations can effectively map and anticipate changes to keep their strategic plans relevant in uncertain environments. This study explores how strategic foresight practices can be used to support the maintenance of a Technological Roadmap at an R&D institute, reducing uncertainty and mitigating its limitations. We demonstrate how foresight frameworks - such as environmental scanning, scenario planning, and expert forecasting - complement the goal-oriented nature of roadmapping. These methods provide a systematic way to identify emerging trends and incorporate potential disruptions, creating a more robust planning process. By detailing the structure and outputs of foresight workshops, we present a practical case for

using these techniques to refine and dynamically update a Technological Roadmap. The result is the transformation of the roadmap from a static plan into a living strategic tool that enables organizations to navigate complexity by continuously exploring future possibilities and adapting to change. This approach directly engages with the colloquium's core themes of Futures, Foresight and Trends, AI and Trend Research, and Trend Methodologies, offering a tangible method for anticipating the transformations ahead.

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

III TRENDS AND CULTURE MANAGEMENT COLLOQUIUM

RE:TREND

CULTURE IN MOTION

